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Work Package 7
Data interoperability and data sharing

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Executive Summary

The goal of WP7 is to ensure sustainability of data formats, identifiers and data access procedures of the HEAP Information Commons (IC) based on the FAIR data management principles. WP7 provides a collection of software solutions (the HEAP FAIR toolbox), training and hands-on activities (Bring Your Own Data workshops) and data quality monitoring services (HEAP FAIR Self-Assessment-Service). D7.2 gives a detailed report on these three components.

As stated in the HEAP Data Management Plan (DMP), the HEAP project and its Information Commons (IC) follow the "FAIR" principles, meaning "Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable". The FAIR principles ensure soundly managed data, leading to knowledge discovery and innovation, and to subsequent data and knowledge integration and reuse, which is evaluated by the FAIR Self-Assessment-Service to ensure the data will be made findable and accessible within the HEAP consortium, and to the broader research community, stakeholders, and policy makers. Also, data must be compliant with national and European ethic-legal framework, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

The HEAP FAIR toolbox is a collection of dockerized software solutions for FAIR data management and analysis based on the Basic Infrastructure Building Box (BIBBOX). With the help of HEAP FAIR toolbox apps can be extended with a FAIR Data Point (FDP), which adds to a local data management solution a machine-readable metadata interface (using the DCAT format) and connects the local app to the central HEAP catalogue.

At the Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops, HEAP researchers brought their example data to test different components of the HEAP platform. In the first two BYOD workshops, FAIR data management training was conducted and the technical solutions of the HEAP Information Commons (IC) and Hopsworks were tested on the basis of sample data.

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List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BIBBOX	Basic Infrastructure Building Box
BYOD	Bring Your Own Data
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
CSC	IT Center for Science, Finland
CSV	Comma-Seperated-Values
DBMS	DataBase Management System
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
FDP	FAIR Data Point
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FMC	Finnish Maternity Cohort
FUSE	File System in User Space
GRLC	GLRC generates restful APIs using SPARQL queries stored in Github repositories
HAPI	Open-source reference implementation of the FHIR specifications in Java
HATEOAS	Hypermedia as the Engine of Application State
HL7	Health Level Seven International
HopsFS	Hopsworks File System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HW	Hopsworks

IC	Information Commons
LDP	Linked Data Platform
LIMS	Laboratory-Information- and Management-System
ML	Machine Learning
NGRX	Framework for building reactive applications in Angula
ORM	Object Relational Mapper
PCJ	Java library
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RedCap	Secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
SAS	Self-Assessment-Service
SD	Sensitive Data
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SPARK	Framework for Computer Clustering
STD	sexually transmitted diseases
UI	User Interface
VM	Virtual Machine

1 Introduction

The aim of work package 7 is data interoperability and data sharing, which is achieved through the establishment of a FAIR Toolbox, the FAIR Self-Assessment-Service and the organisation of BYOD workshops within HEAP.

The main sections in this deliverable are the description of the toolbox including installed apps as well as the explanation of the FAIR Data Points within the BIBBOX (as a building box for software solutions). Additionally, the FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service, which evaluates and offers support for researchers reviewing their data according to the FAIR-principles, is described. Supporting WP11, FAIR Data videos are being produced, easily explaining what the FAIR principles are about and how they can be useful for every researcher. This and in general the whole practical implementation was successfully created and developed in the first two BYOD workshops, which have taken place in year 1 and year 2 of HEAP.

All the sections in this document underlie the principles of FAIR (further explained in the following chapter) and are the basis for the realisation of a platform, which will provide a system for obtaining, managing, sharing, and analysing exposome data. The criteria to evaluate the FAIR principles are based on the FAIR Data Maturity Model Guideline [1] and propose the idea that data must be stored, shared, and used in a FAIR standard - that is to say: findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable.

2 FAIR Toolbox

The FAIR toolbox is based on the BIBBOX framework for the integration of data from different stakeholders, such as biobanking, biomedical research, healthcare, and other social organizations. In the following, we further explain the content of the FAIR toolbox based on the Basic Infrastructure Building Box (BIBBOX), which provides software solutions in form of apps for biobanking and bioinformatics as e.g., Openspecimen, Molgenis or Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR).

2.1 FAIR Tools in our FAIR Toolbox

Our FAIR Toolbox makes various tools readily available and easy to install. Installed apps can easily be served directly to the end-user. It is possible to integrate every app that is or can be dockerized into the FAIR Toolbox and thereby extend available services. In the current state, most of the implemented apps are aimed towards biobanking, biomedical research, healthcare, and Data-Management. We present here a comprehensive list of implemented FAIR Tools. The main FAIR tools are described in more detail:

Openspecimen

OpenSpecimen is a biobank/biospecimen management tool. OpenSpecimen can be used to manage quality, request and distribution of individual biospecimens and entire collections. OpenSpecimen is highly configurable and customizable to improve efficiency and ease of handling. The easy-to-use interface allows users to create and manage catalogues within OpenSpecimen. Catalogues can be configured to only expose data which should be unveiled and hide other (sensitive) data. Although OpenSpecimen offers a web-based frontend interface for the general user it is also possible to use the REST API (Application Programming Interface) for data interactions.

Molgenis

Molgenis is a web-based application for management of scientific data. The entire data model consisting of various entities and variables is highly flexible and configurable. A user-friendly interface allows capturing, exchanging, and the exploitation of large amounts of data. Molgenis helps to make the data FAIR and makes it easy to share and re-use data. The fine-grained permission system allows to expose the appropriate data without exposing (sensitive) data. Genomic data can be visualised right out-of-the-box. Molgenis further allows to run computational scripts for data analysis. Molgenis also offers a REST API to connect to the data from an analysis script or a custom plugin.

HAPI-FHIR

Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) is a standard published by Health Level Seven International (HL7) for data exchange in the healthcare sector. HAPI-FHIR is a Java implementation of a FHIR store. The focus of FHIR is to provide interoperability and simultaneously offer flexibility. Resources of the healthcare system are present in the FHIR standard but can easily be extended without losing the interoperability if necessary. Common web standards (e.g., XML, JSON, HTTP) are used to import, export and exchange data via a REST API.

Jupyter Notebook

A Jupyter Notebook is a web-based tool used for interactive computing. A Jupyter Notebook is suitable for developing, documenting, and executing code, as well as communicating the results. Jupyter Notebook can be used to create interactive documents; however, it can also be used to share these interactive documents.

Further Tools

There are many more tools supported in our toolbox, besides the main tools described above, as listed in Table 1:

Logo	Name	Description
	Omero	Managing, visualizing and analyzing microscopy images and associated metadata.
	DSpace	Fluid modern document management tool with flexible data structure.
	SeedDMS	Document management system with an easy-to-use web-based user interface.
	RedCap	Secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases.
	Wordpress	Software to create beautiful websites, blogs, or apps.
	LimeSurvey	Versatile online survey tool.
	PostgreSQL	A powerful object-relational database system.
	Adminer	Tool for managing content in databases and consists of only a single PHP file.
	PhenoTips	Software for medical genetics, complete with pedigree charts, Human Phenotype Ontology capture, diagnostic insights for rare diseases and more.
	Galaxy	Platform for FAIR data analysis that ensures reproducibility, allows to manage and share data, and enables the use of tools from various domains.
	TAIGA	Project management tool for multifunctional agile teams.
	Mantis	Issue tracker that makes collaboration with team members & clients easy, fast, and professional.
	XNAT	Imaging informatics platform for management, productivity, and quality assurance tasks of imaging and associated data.

Logo	Name	Description
	ELabFTW	Electronic Lab Notebook

Table 1: Further Tools in the FAIR Toolbox

2.2 FAIR Data Points-BIBBOX

FAIR Toolbox

The Basic Infrastructure Building Box (BIBBOX - <http://bibbox.bbmri-eric.eu>) was used as a basis to build a FAIR Toolbox. BIBBOX is a modular, component-based toolkit for biobanks and bioinformatics. BIBBOX provides an app store for software solutions mainly in the fields biobanking and bioinformatics.

The BIBBOX was upgraded to version 4 and now allows the extension of BIBBOX Apps with a FAIR Data Point (FDP). This is particularly useful if a BIBBOX App represents a catalogue (e.g., OpenSpecimen as sample management) or a repository for digital objects (e.g., dSpace and seedDMS). In addition, the FDP component can also be used to create a catalogue for all BIBBOX Apps. In such a case, it is a catalogue of catalogues.

BIBBOX Apps consist of a dockerized open-source software tool. Either the official published docker image or if none is available a docker image is published in the BIBBOX Docker Hub. Through containerization, a simple and consistent deployment is also possible for non-technical users. The base docker images are integrated with supporting services such as database and monitoring, creating a docker compose file that can be installed as a standalone app. It is possible to integrate FDP components with the app. Each app is published to a GitHub repository according to a defined procedure.

Figure 1: FAIR Data Point (FDP) architecture

The FAIR Data principles do not propose or promote any particular technology. However, a FAIR Data Point (FDP) provides an implementation of the principles using existing standards with a defined API endpoint. In the GoFair project, the following 3 content requirements were defined for a FDP [2]:

- The first and most important requirement is the definition of the API for the FDP. The API is based entirely on semantic metadata standards such as the Data Catalog (DCAT) and Dublin Core, combined with the Linked Data Platform (LDP) principle and RESTful APIs. This combination aims at the highest possible technical interoperability in combination with a relatively simple implementation.
- The second requirement is an authentication system that allows FDP operators to define and update metadata and grant public read-only access.
- The third requirement is a web frontend that can be used to add and edit or query the information in the metadata registry service. As an editor, it contains a simple validation of data types based on the Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL). It facilitates the creation of metadata profiles as well as their filling but is intended only as a support for an FDP and not as a replacement for complete metadata profile development systems.

Based on the reference implementation of a FDP, an extension component for BIBBOX Apps was developed. The FAIR Data Point is a software that, on the one hand, enables data controllers to publish datasets in a FAIR-compliant manner and, on the other hand, allows data users to analyse

metadata properties about the offered datasets and, if the licensing conditions allow, to access the data itself. A key architectural requirement is that FDPs are distributed. This allows an FDP to be integrated with other applications and to be included in a network of FDPs through the defined API. A FDP consists of four main modules (which implement the three requirements), namely the Metadata Provider, the FAIR Accessor, the Metrics Gatherer, and the Security Enforcer.

Figure 2: FAIR Data Point Structure (Figure taken from [2])

Module	Description
FDP - Metadata Provider	The Metadata Provider is responsible for accessing the metadata. The component can be controlled via a REST API. The Hypermedia as the Engine of Application State (HATEOAS) is used as the design pattern.

Module	Description
FDP - FAIR Accessor	The FAIR Accessor component provides access to the actual data content of the dataset. The W3C standard Linked Data Platform (LDP) is used to implement the FDP - FAIR Accessor. LDP defines a set of rules for HTTP to web resources and provides an architecture for Linked Data with read and write access on the web.
FDP - Metrics Gatherer	The Metrics Gatherer component monitors various aspects of FDP usage. These metrics can be used by the FDP owner to assess the utilisation of their FDPs. Since one of the FAIR Data principles requires citability of data, an equivalent to the impact factor of scientific journals can be derived from the information about the usage of published data.
FDP - Security Enforcer	The Security Enforcer acts as a gatekeeper to the (meta) data and can encrypt data during backup, storage, and transmission. This allows the FDP owner to commission any cloud storage provider without having to consider the cloud's security features. The Security Enforcer also offers an optional service for pseudo-anonymization of data.

Table 2: Module description

The 4 components (Metadata Provider, FAIR Accessor, Metrics Gatherer and the Security Enforcer) are combined in a Docker Image and published in the BIBBOX Docker Hub for the extension of any BIBBOX App with a FDP. This in combination with a database (Virtuoso) results in the BIBBOX FDP extension.

A Jupyter Notebook is used as a link (middle component) between a specific app/software, e.g., the sample management tool OpenSpecimen. This Jupyter Notebook contains on the one hand the possibility to configure the FDP and to synchronize (meta) data between app and FDP, and on the other hand the functionality of a FDP can be documented. Alternatively, it is possible to transfer the scripts implemented in the Jupyter Notebook directly into an app.

Fair Data Point Docker Containers bibbox/img-fair-data-point, tenforce/virtuoso	FAIR DATA POINT
Jupyter Data Science Notebook jupyter/datascience-notebook	Control & Demo Console
App Specific Docker Containers bibbox/app-containers (e.g. OpenSpecimen), other official containers	APP HCI APP specific APIs

Figure 3: Structure of a BIBBOX app including the FDP extension

Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT)

Sharing data resources among different organizations, researchers, governments, and citizens requires the provision of metadata. This is true whether the data is publicly available or not. Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) is a Resource Description Framework (RDF) vocabulary that enables interoperability between data catalogues published on the web. DCAT allows records and data services to be described in a catalogue using a standard model and vocabulary, as well as merging metadata from multiple catalogues. This improves the findability of datasets and data services and enables a decentralized approach to publishing data catalogues, as well as federated searching for datasets in catalogues at multiple sites [3]. DCAT itself does not yet specify the serialization format of datasets, but it does distinguish between the abstract dataset and its various manifestations. DCAT datasets can be represented in many forms, including RDF accessible through SPARQL endpoints, embedded in HTML pages as HTML RDFa, or serialized as RDF/XML, N3, Turtle, JSON-LD, or other formats. Further on, the examples are presented in Turtle. DCAT is based on six main classes.

Class	Description
Catalogue	dcat:Catalog represents a catalogue, i.e. a data set in which each individual element is a metadata record describing a resource.
Resources	dcat:Resource represents a dataset, a data service or any other data object that can be described by a metadata record in a catalogue. This class is not intended for direct use, but is the parent class of dcat:Dataset, dcat:DataService, and dcat:Catalog.

Class	Description
Dataset	dcap:Dataset represents a dataset. A dataset is a collection of data published or curated by a single actor.
Distribution	dcap:Distribution represents an accessible form of a data set, e.g. a downloadable file.
Data Service	dcap:DataService represents a data service, which is a collection of operations accessible through an interface, an Application Programming Interface (API).
Catalogue Record	dcap:CatalogRecord represents a metadata element in the catalogue that primarily concerns registration information, such as who added the element and when.

Table 3: DCAT distinction

Implementation

The deployed FAIR toolbox architecture allows for each app to be deployed independently. The implementation of the FAIR-toolbox uses various common technologies. Apps are integrated in the FAIR toolbox framework via the FDP-Integration extension. The FDP-Integration extension consists of docker containers, which “FAIRify” a base application.

A short overview of the used technologies in the FAIR toolbox framework is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Overview of FAIR Toolbox architecture as it is deployed in the BIBBOX

Technology	Description
Docker	Docker is a virtualization of software. Software tools are packaged in docker containers.
Flask	Flask is a widely used open-source web framework for Python.
SQLAlchemy	SQLAlchemy is a program library for simple interaction between Flask and a database. As an abstraction layer, it simplifies the use of the database by providing, among other things, an Object Relational Mapper (ORM).
Celery	Celery is a task manager, which distributes tasks to worker instances. Celery usually uses a message broker such as Redis for the distribution of tasks.
Redis	Redis is an in-memory data structure store, used as a (NoSQL) database, cache, and message broker.

Technology	Description
Swagger	Swagger is a language to describe REST APIs. The OpenAPI specification is used as the underlying standard.
Apache HTTPD	The Apache HTTP web server is one of the most popular web server implementations in the world. This web server is open-source, robust, flexible, simple and secure.
Angular	Angular is a frontend typescript framework for scalable applications. Angular uses NGRX as a state management library, which implements a "store".

Table 4: FAIR Toolbox architecture

FAIR DataPoint Docker

A "FAIRified" app consists of a base application, middleware (software for communication between software components, e.g., Jupyter Notebook), and FAIR Data Point components. These individual components were bundled as docker containers. Essential containers are the FDP-Flask container, the Virtuoso container, and the Jupyter Notebook container. As an optional container, a GRLC (SPAQRL-Query API) container may also be included - this enables more complex search queries for the metadata.

Figure 5: Schematic Structure of a "FAIRified" app. The base app is extended with FDP containers.

FDP Flask Server

Flask is used as the central component of the FDP. The API is automatically generated from the API blueprint (OpenAPI specification) using Swagger. Metadata to be entered into the database using the API is validated beforehand. This validation is implemented using the pyshacl program library, as well as defined SHACL schemas. The database connection between Flask and SPARQL is provided by functionalities within the rdflib program library, which connects Flask to the database container.

FDP-Virtuoso

Virtuoso is a combination of middleware and a DataBase Management System (DBMS). Virtuoso provides the link between Flask and the database in the FDP extension by allowing the RDF-based data to be used via SPARQL.

RDF data (based on Resource Description Framework data scheme) are also called triples because it consists of three different entities. These are subject, predicate, and object. The predicate expresses relationships between the entities of such triples. Those relationships can be visualized as a graph. A graph database is a collection of such relationships. While in relational databases relationships between entities are described only in terms of their cardinality, in a graph database the relationships between entities are specified by defined types.

Middleware

A Jupyter Notebook can be used as middleware between the base app (e.g. sample management app OpenSpecimen) and the FDP API. A Jupyter Notebook is a web-based tool for creating and sharing interactive documents. The interactive element in this case is Python code. By using Jupyter Notebooks in comparison to pure Python scripts, program flows can be better documented, etc. However, the code could also be integrated directly into the code from the FDP-Flask server.

The two most important components for a successful interaction between sample management app and FDP are base app API connector and FDP client.

The Base-App API-Connector is responsible for retrieving the relevant metadata from existing sample management apps e.g., the OpenSpecimenAPIconnector can be used. This component must be reprogrammed for different apps since the structure of the sample management apps differs from app to app, or different metadata are collected, etc.

The FDP Client is responsible for feeding the metadata received from Base-App API Connector into the FAIR Data Point using FDP API calls. The FDP client module is designed to interact with the FDP server using CRUD

(create, read, update, delete) operations. Since the structure of the FDP server does not change, regardless of the linked sample management app, this module does not change. Currently, CRUD operations are implemented for the following resources: r3d:repository, dcat:catalog, dcat:dataset, dcat:distribution.

FDP Search extension via GRLC

As an optional container, GRLC can be added to the docker compose file to provide specific API endpoints in addition to the API endpoints provided by the FDP Flask server to search the graph database based on SPARQL queries. GRLC generates OpenAPI compliant API endpoints depending on the provided SPARQL queries and makes them available.

Integration of FDP-Components in OpenSpecimen

Apps in the FAIR toolbox consist of individual docker services, each of which is combined in a docker compose file for each app. To "FAIRify" an app, all that needs to be done is to add the FDP services to the app's docker compose file. The docker compose file is automatically generated based on a template when installed in the BIBBOX web interface. During the installation all necessary parameters are provided by the user and used to fill out the template.

Example of a generated "FAIRified" docker-compose file:

```
services:
# Base App: consists of services openspecimen-web & openspecimen-db
openspecimen-web:
  image: bibbox/openspecimen:v8-0-x
  container_name: openspecimen-web
  restart: unless-stopped
  networks:
    - bibbox-default-network
  links:
    - openspecimen-db:openspecimen-db
  environment:
    - DATABASE_HOST=openspecimen-db
    - MYSQL_ROOT_PASSWORD=openspecimen
    - MYSQL_DATABASE=openspecimen
    - MYSQL_USER=openspecimen
    - MYSQL_PASSWORD=openspecimen
    - TOMCAT_MANAGER_USER=openspecimen
    - TOMCAT_MANAGER_PASSWORD=openspecimen
    - INSTITUTE_NAME=BIBBOX Demo Biobank
    - EMAIL_ADRESS="admin@bibbox.org"
    - FIRST_NAME=admin
    - LAST_NAME=Bibbox
    - LOGIN_NAME=bibboxadmin
  depends_on:
    - openspecimen-db
  volumes:
    - ./data/os-data:/var/lib/openspecimen/data
    - ./data/os-plugins:/var/lib/openspecimen/plugins
  ports:
    - "9000:8080"
openspecimen-db:
  image: mysql:8.0
```

```

container_name: openspecimen-db
restart: unless-stopped
networks:
  - bibbox-default-network
environment:
  - MYSQL_ROOT_PASSWORD=openspecimen
  - MYSQL_DATABASE=openspecimen
  - MYSQL_USER=openspecimen
  - MYSQL_PASSWORD=openspecimen
volumes:
  - ./data/mysql:/var/lib/mysql
  - ./configs/openspecimen.cnf:/etc/mysql/conf.d/openspecimen.cnf
# fdp containers
jupyter: # Jupyter Notebook Service
image: jupyter/datascience-notebook # official jupyter baseimage
container_name: jupyter
restart: unless-stopped
networks:
  - bibbox-default-network
# The FDP-Search-API can be reached via http://0.0.0.0:8008.
ports:
  - "8008:8008"
volumes:
  - ./home/jovyan/work:/home/jovyan/work
fdp: # fdp-flask service
image: bibbox/fairdatapoint # modified fairdatapoint image
restart: unless-stopped
depends_on:
  - virtuoso
# The FDP-Search-API can be reached via http://0.0.0.0:8008.
environment:
  - FDP_HOST: "0.0.0.0"
  - FDP_PORT: "8888"
fdpsearch:
# SPARQL-Query Service; optional
image: nlesc/fairdatapoint-search # baseimage
restart: unless-stopped
# The FDP-Search-API can be reached via http://0.0.0.0:8008.
ports:
  - "8088:8088"
environment:
  - GRQC_SPARQL_ENDPOINT=http://virtuoso:8890/sparql
  - DEBUG=false
depends_on:
  - virtuoso
virtuoso:
image: tenforce/virtuoso # baseimage
restart: unless-stopped
environment:
  - SPARQL_UPDATE=true
volumes:
  - ./data/virtuoso:/data
# A network is defined, to enable the communication
# between services
networks:
  bibbox-default-network:
    external: true

```

Figure 6: Example of a docker-compose file

3 FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service

As part of task 7.3 to evaluate the interoperability and the FAIRness of the cohort's data sets, which will be assessed and reviewed later within deliverable D7.6, we developed a software tool, the FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service. Due to the pandemic and several related delays in this regard, the establishment of the FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service has been delayed.

The guided Self-Assessment is supposed to help and assist HEAP researchers to understand whether their data and metadata is FAIR. According to the FAIR Data Maturity Model [1], the FAIR principles are defined as "inspiring concepts... that enable both machines and humans to find, access, interoperate and re-use data and metadata". The service shall assess (first guided, then independently) the quality of how data is stored, can be accessed, worked with and re-used by the same or other researchers in the future.

Our Self-Assessment-Service (SAS) to evaluate whether data that meet the criteria of being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) is based on the FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines. This FAIR data model framework consists of indicators, priorities, and evaluation methods. Indicators are derived from the FAIR principals and represent measurable aspects of each principle. We adopted the indicators developed by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model [1]. See list of some Indicators in Figure 7.

FAIR	ID	Indicator	Priority
F1	RDA-F1-01M	Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier	●●● Essential
F1	RDA-F1-01D	Data is identified by a persistent identifier	●●● Essential
F1	RDA-F1-02M	Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier	●●● Essential
F1	RDA-F1-02D	Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	●●● Essential
F2	RDA-F2-01M	Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	●●● Essential
F3	RDA-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier for the data	●●● Essential
F4	RDA-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-01M	Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	●● Important
A1	RDA-A1-02M	Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-02D	Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-03M	Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-03D	Data identifier resolves to a digital object	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-04M	Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-04D	Data is accessible through standardised protocol	●●● Essential
A1	RDA-A1-05D	Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)	●● Important
A1.1	RDA-A1.1-01M	Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol	●●● Essential
A1.1	RDA-A1.1-01D	Data is accessible through a free access protocol	●● Important
A1.2	RDA-A1.2-01D	Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation	● Useful

Figure 7: Examples of Indicators F (findable) and A (accessible)

In Figure 7, some indicators are listed regarding the principles Findability and Accessibility.

Furthermore, priorities were assigned to the indicators, namely one of three priority levels: Essential, Important or Useful.

Further definition of Indicator priorities [4]:

Essential: Such an indicator addresses an aspect that is of the utmost importance to achieve FAIRness under most circumstances, or, conversely, FAIRness would be practically impossible to achieve if the indicator were not satisfied.

Important: Such an indicator addresses an aspect that might not be of the utmost importance under specific circumstances, but its satisfaction, if at all possible, would substantially increase FAIRness.

Useful: Such an indicator addresses an aspect that is nice-to-have but is not necessarily indispensable.

Two different evaluation methods are presented by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group to evaluate and measure the individual indicators “measuring progress” and “measuring pass-or-fail”. We opted to use the measuring progress as it is best suited to answer the question of “How can the FAIRness of this data be improved?”. For each indicator the maturity level is determined. It is necessary to assign a numeric value to each maturity level in order to display an indicator's maturity level in a spider graph (Figure 8). To get an overview of the current FAIRness of a data set our SAS generates a report, which includes 4 spider graphs. Each spider graph represents one of the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability).

Maturity level per indicator (per FAIR area)
0 - not applicable
1 - not being considered this yet
2 - under consideration or in planning phase
3 - in implementation phase
4 - fully implemented

Figure 8: Five maturity levels

Data is collected via a RedCap questionnaire based on the guidelines described above. The maturity level for each indicator is collected. Our SAS Reporting tool was created as a Java Service - based on SPARK (Framework for Computer Clustering). The service is triggered when a questionnaire is completed. It collects data from the RedCap questionnaire and automatically generates a report, which is sent to the given contact and if specified to the HEAP-Team. The user can specify if they create the report for themselves for internal use or also like to share the data with the Consortium. The report is generated using TIBCO JasperSoft. To generate the report, we created a JasperSoft JRXML template. Our service fills the template variables with data collected in RedCap. Based on the data, the appropriate maturity level of the individual indicator is “checked” (Figure 9). In this example, the maturity level 2 - under consideration or in planning phase - is checked/selected. Furthermore, the indicator ID (F1-01M) and the priority level (Essential) is visible.

F1-01M Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier

●●● Essential

- 0 - not applicable
- 1 - not being considered yet
- 2 - under consideration or in planning phase
- 3 - in implementation phase
- 4 - fully implemented

Figure 9: Example of one indicator in the final report.

Spider Graph

A spider graph, spider chart or radar chart is a two-dimensional chart to display multivariate data. The spider graph can display multiple quantitative variables as long as they have the same range (e.g., from 0 to 4). Each variable is represented by an axis, the relative position and angle of the axes is typically uninformative (Figure 10). Values of adjacent variables (axes) are connected by a line. It is also possible to plot multiple data series, which share the same variables in one spider graph. In this case, each series is represented by a different line.

Figure 10: Schematic spider graph

JasperSoft allows you to generate spider graphs. However, this can only be done if the data is correctly provided. Data must be aggregated to a matrix and cannot be provided as singular variables of different values. The RedCap data needed to be put into a tabular/matrix format with the columns Series, Values and Categories for each FAIR principle. Indicators are in the category column and the corresponding numeric maturity level values are in the values column. An internal mapping of indicators to indicatorID is necessary. The spider graph can only display numeric values. Therefore, a

conversion of maturity level to numeric values is also necessary. It was also necessary to include the original data in the data tabular/matrix in addition to the aggregated categories and values columns. As the original data is used to fill in the maturity level of each indicator in the report.

We tried to improve the spider graph design over multiple iterations. We aimed to improve readability and interpretability with each iteration. The different spider graph design versions can be seen in Figure 11-Figure 15.

Figure 11: Version 1 of spider graph

Figure 12: Version 2 of spider graph. Category/Indicator labels were changed to their ID to improve readability

Figure 13: Version 3 of spider graph. Margin was increased to improve readability.

Figure 14: Final version of spider graph. Markings for the maturity levels from 0 not applicable to 4 fully implemented were added.

Figure 15: Definite spider graph design for each FAIR principle in a 2 by 2 grid.

Banner Design

Concerning the designing of the banner as well as the designing for the logo composition for the SAS, we followed the official guidelines of the website of the project HEAP.

Additionally, the final banner design for the report of the SAS was implemented in accordance with the HEAP graphic guidelines.

Figure 16: Final banner design for the report of the Self-Assessment-Service

Design Phases - Questionnaire

Resize font:
+ | -

Fair Data Self-Assessment-Tool for HEAP

Please complete the survey below.

Thank you!

Contact person's email address

Indicators for Findable

Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier

- 0 - not applicable
- 1 - not being considered yet
- 2 - under consideration or in planning phase
- 3 - in implementation phase
- 4 - fully implemented

Essential

reset

Figure 17: First version of the RedCap questionnaire

The initial draft of the questionnaire for the Self-Assessment-Service can be seen in Figure 17. The following steps were taken iteratively in order to improve usability. The final version can be seen in Figure 19.

1. Making the questionnaire and generated report distinct

Using the following attributes, a report can be clearly linked to a specific data cohort, even if one person filled out the questionnaire for multiple, different cohorts:

- Cohort name
- Cohort ID (required)
- Institution
- Name of the contact person

The introduction of the Cohort ID (defined by the user) allows for a clear distinction and together with the date the questionnaire was answered,

multiple reports can be clearly linked to a data cohort in the correct order, regardless of the contact person.

To further facilitate the easy linkage of a report to the data cohort, a variable filename for the report was introduced. The reports filename follows the following convention:

“Report - HEAP FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service - *date* - *cohort_id*”

- *date* refers to the date the questionnaire was filled out and submitted
- *cohort_id* refers to the Cohort ID provided in the questionnaire

2. Facilitate ease of use

To facilitate the usability of the questionnaire as well as the report, we implemented introductory texts, giving a summary of the Self-Assessment-Service’s aims. This should be especially helpful in cases, where the people working with the report are not the ones who took the questionnaire.

The report’s introduction also explains spider graphs and restates the 5 maturity levels of each FAIR indicator (see Figure 8).

To help people fill out the questionnaire correctly, help-texts were included with each question. The texts were taken from the FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines, 2020 [1]. The implementation of the tooltips was done using the REDCap external module “Form Field Tooltip” in the version 3.2. The module is part of the REDCap third-party module repository and can also be found on GitHub.

The tooltips are shown, when the user hovers the mouse cursor over the information icon (white ‘I’ on blue round background), which can be seen in Figure 18. In this example, the tooltip for question A1-04D is displayed.

not being considered yet

phase

reset

A1-04D Data access protocol **Essential**

Assessment details
This indicator can be evaluated by looking at the way the data can be accessed.
Common data access protocols are HTTP and FTP, DAP₂₂ and JSON-RPC₂₃.

phase

reset

Figure 18: Question A1-04D with tooltip

FAIR Data Self-Assessment-Service for HEAP

This survey evaluates the "FAIRness level" of the HEAP cohorts, showing how well data and data management practices perform under each FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reuseable) category, highlighting any areas covered in the assessment that need further work.

Please complete the survey below.

Thank you!

Cohort name	<input type="text"/>
Cohort ID <small>* must provide value</small>	<input type="text"/>
Institution	<input type="text"/>
Contact person	<input type="text"/>
Contact person's email address <small>* must provide value</small>	<input type="text"/>
Generate and send PDF report <small>* must provide value</small>	<input type="radio"/> Generate report for internal use <input type="radio"/> Generate report and submit results to HEAP

[reset](#)

Indicators for Findable

F1-01M Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier ● ● ● **Essential**

* must provide value

1

0 - not applicable
 1 - not being considered yet
 2 - under consideration or in planning phase
 3 - in implementation phase
 4 - fully implemented

[reset](#)

Figure 19: Final version of the RedCap questionnaire

3.1 FAIR Data Videos

In accordance with WP11, the FAIR data videos have been under development. WP11 is leading the production and creation of the FAIR videos, together with a graphic and communication company. WP7 has taken on the technical content, both for the development and advisory role.

FAIR Toolbox Video Series – Description

The aim of the video series is to provide an engaging way to support researchers or other future users of the HEAP platform to ensure their data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) before upload. The potential audience is wider than HEAP users, and the series will take a generic approach to FAIR best practice, using HEAP as a practical example.

It is planned that five videos of approximately 4 minutes each, using a mixture of recorded interviews and animations, will be produced as a whole.

Design Phase (Part 1)

The source material for the video series was gathered with the help of the HEAP project partners at the second Bring-Your-Own-Data (BYOD) workshop and a series of follow up meetings.

The creative concepts and animation technical requirements for the video series, along with the final scripts and storyboards for the videos, was developed by a Science Communication Agency working closely with the HEAP partners.

4 BYOD Workshops

Together with WP11, WP7 is organising BYOD-workshops throughout the course of the duration of HEAP, providing all HEAP project partners with hands-on trainings (hackathon) to improve and evaluate the interoperability and FAIRness of their data sets within HEAP. The Bring-Your-Own-Data (BYOD) workshops are inspired by the Bring-Your-Own-Device movement but instead of an electronical device, researchers are supposed to bring their data and metadata from their respective cohorts. The workshops are built as hackathons/hands-on trainings, in which researchers work interoperably with each other and with their real or mock-up data in sessions coding or take API tests or assessments.

4.1 BYOD-Workshop #1

The first Bring-Your-Own-Data workshop within HEAP was originally designed as f2f-meeting, however, due to the international COVID-19 related restrictions, the workshop was held virtually over a period of 3 days from December 16th to December 18th, 2020. Almost 40 project partners and researchers participated in the online training sessions and lectures including case studies of the then 5 different health cohorts of the project.

The following list states all participants of the 1st BYOD-workshop and which of the two parallel streams they attended.

Institution	Name	Attendance
KI	Joakim Dillner	Training
KI	Helena Andersson	Stream A
KI	Roxana Merino Martinez	Stream A
KI	Suyesh Amatya	Stream A
KI	Mark Clements	Training
KI	Sara Arroyo Muhr	Training, Stream A
KI	Michael Snyder	Stream A
KI	Allison Zhang	Stream A
SSI	Bartłomiej Wilkowski	Stream A
SSI	Steven Chong	Stream A

Institution	Name	Attendance
SSI	Frederik Trier Möller	Training
MLC	Evert-Ben van Veen	Training
MLC	Daniel Gross	Training
MLC	Martin Boeckhout	Training
MUG	Heimo Müller	Training, Stream B
MUG	Andreas Holzinger	Training, Stream B
MUG	Bettina Kipperer	Training, Stream B
MUG	Markus Plass	Training, Stream B
MUG	Robert Reihs	Stream A, Training
MUG	Stefan Herdy	Stream A, Training
ICM	Łukasz Górski	Training, Stream B
ICM	Magdalena Mroczek	Training, Stream A
LC	Jim Dowling	Training
LC	Alex Ormenisan	Training
IARC	Anouk Berger	Training, Stream B
IARC	Zisis Kozlakidis	Training, Stream B
IARC	Julie Roux	Training, Stream B
IARC	Heather Coombs	Training, Stream B
INSB	Chiara Maria Stella Herzog	Training, Stream A
OULU	Helja-Marja Surcel	Training
OULU	Hanna Öhman	Training
CSC	Stefan Negru	Training, Stream B
CSC	Juha Törnroos	Stream B

Institution	Name	Attendance
CSC	Minna Ahokas	Training, Stream B
Tampere	Ville Pimenoff	Training

Agenda

16.12.2020	Plenary	
9:00 - 9:30 (CET)	Introduction (JD), goals of the meeting, zoom housekeeping, introduction round (HM)	
9:30-11:30 (CET)	The Data Management Plan – How HEAP will become FAIR (HM)	
11:30-12:00 (CET)	Jamboree goals by the stream chairs (RM, AB)	
	Jamboree Streams	
	Stream A (RM)	Stream B (AB)
13:00 – 17:00 (CET)	Cohorts metadata topic 1: Metadata for sequencing data (KI, TAUH) topic2: Metadata for consumers (SSI)	Future Training & Services topic 1: Data management in HW (LC, CSC) topic 2: Metadata designer/assigner
17.12.2020	Plenary	
9:00 - 9:30 (CET)	Report on day 1 from the stream chairs	
9:30-12:00 (CET)	HEAP Data Management Services	
	Jamboree Streams	
	Stream A (RM)	Stream B (AB)
13:00 – 17:00 (CET)	Cohorts metadata topic 1: Harmonisation of sequencing data from the data providers. Include analysis metadata (KI (PEM), TAUH, ICM) Topic 2: Consumer cohort data harmonisation. How to integrate it into the HEAP?	Future Training & Services topic 1: Metadata in HW (LC). Implementing sequencing metadata in HW

18.12.2020	Plenary
9:00 - 10:30 (CET)	Report on day 2 and conclusion from the stream chairs (each 30 min)
11:00 - 11:30 (CET)	HEAP Self-Assessment Service (SAS)
12:30-13:00 (CET)	Wrap up and closing

In the beginning of the first BYOD-workshop, all the participants were again familiarised with the Data Management Plan (DMP), which clarified what the HEAP Information Commons (IC) should contain as well as how to make the data, which all of the researchers in HEAP are using, FAIR in order to work with the data metadata now and in the future.

Data Management Plan

Each DMP has the following parts

Figure 20: Description of Data Management Plan (DMP)

To begin with, the five already existing cohorts were introduced to all the HEAP partners in a very detailed way:

1. Cervical Screening Cohort

Data is collected from the samples taken in the organised cervical screening program in Stockholm region and national health registers and quality register databases. The registered data is collected in SAS and MySQL and stored in LIMS (Laboratory-Information- and

Management-System) and in CSV (comma-separated-values) format. This data and metadata are uploaded to Hopworks (HW) to be used by everyone on the platform.

2. Maternity Cohort

The origin of the data is the Finnish National Prenatal screening, additionally FMC (Finnish Maternity Cohort) screening results (HIV, syphilis, Hepatitis B, rubella) will be included. The participation data is encrypted as CSV, reports are configured in Word/PDF/HTML files.

3. HPV Vaccination Cohort

All data collected come from the intervention trial follow-up. In addition, STD (sexually transmitted diseases) follow-up results (HPV and chlamydia) will be used. Data is stored in encrypted CSV files and documented as Word, PDF and HTML files.

4. Consumer Cohort

Consumer cohort includes data from commercial digital receipt providers (such as start-up companies), and if possible, loyalty programmes. The data is re-used from other sources such as Danish registers, quality databases, or research projects, as well as digital receipt solutions and loyalty programs. Data is received in a JSON format and saved in MS SQL Database.

5. Wearable Data Collection Study

The study follows 100 pregnant women participating in the Finish Maternity cohort to investigate how the exposome influences the health of the mother and the baby, including environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, airflow-rate and geo-location data.

The aim of the project HEAP is to harmonise metadata within HEAP and other exposome projects by following the FAIR principles, better defined in chapter 3. In order to establish a catalogue, which follows the standards and rules of FAIR, we split the work into 2 streams as can be seen in the following lines:

Stream A

Chair: Roxana Merino Martinez

In Stream A, the leading researchers presented the 5 different cohorts from their respective institutions: Cervical Cancer Screening cohort, Maternity

cohort, HPV Vaccination cohort, Consumers cohort and Wearable Data Collection study. The general aim for this workshop was to establish a standardisation of the metadata, the harmonisation of the cohorts' data and integrate the collected data and metadata of their respective cohort into the open-source Machine Learning platform Hopsworks.

Hopsworks- Platform Introduction and the Usage of Tags

WP6 presentation focused on the initial usage of the platform by involved partners. This involved account creation and introduction of services on the first iteration of the HEAP test bed. This part of the demonstration included creating projects, managing a project's team of users, uploading and downloading data to/from the platform, searching for data on the platform and using notebooks and jobs to run computation on the cluster.

The second part of the demonstration included showing the tagging capabilities of the platform. This included an introduction to the schematized tags and the schemas which follow the reference <https://json-schema.org>.

The demonstration included multiple examples detailing specifics of the json schemas. We started with simple examples as we can see in the figures below, where we described a simple person object with base types such as strings and integers and mark specific fields as being mandatory and that no unspecified fields in the schema could be present in valid json values.

```
{
  "type" : "object",
  "properties" :
  {
    "first_name" : { "type" : "string" },
    "last_name" : { "type" : "string" },
    "age" : { "type" : "integer" },
    "hobbies" : {
      "type" : "array",
      "items" : { "type" : "string" }
    }
  },
  "required" : ["first_name", "last_name", "age"],
  "additionalProperties": false
}
```

For each example of a json schema we also provide a valid json value.

```
{
  "first_name" : "John",
  "last_name" : "Doe",
  "age" : 27,
  "hobbies" : ["tennis", "reading"]
}
```

The examples also include more complex examples of schemas, where we also showed how to use complex schemas, regex patterns, min/max rules.

```
{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    {
      "id": {
        "type": "string",
        "pattern": "^[A-Z]{2}[0-9]{4}$"
      },
      "first_name": { "type": "string" },
      "last_name": { "type": "string" },
      "age": {
        "type": "integer",
        "minimum": 0,
        "maximum": 150
      },
      "hobbies": {
        "type": "array",
        "items": { "type": "string" }
      },
      "address": {
        "street": { "type": "string" },
        "city": { "type": "string" }
      }
    },
    "required": ["id", "first_name", "last_name", "age"],
    "additionalProperties": false
  }
}
```

```
{
  "id" : "AB1234",
  "first_name" : "John",
  "last_name" : "Doe",
  "age" : 27,
  "hobbies" : ["tennis", "reading"],
  "address" : {
    "street" : "Vasagatan nr. 12",
    "city" : "Stockholm"
  }
}
```

The demonstration also included examples on how to add, remove or read tags attached to datasets. These tags can be managed from both a notebook, as well as from the UI. Once attached to datasets, the tags values can also be used to assist in the searching of data. The demonstration showed we can use the tags values, through full text search to discover more easily the datasets from our platform.

HEAP Data Management Services

After the introduction of the Hopsworks platform, WP10 focused its presentation on services provided by CSC as part of the Human Exposome Assessment Platform and their progress and interaction at this stage of the project.

1. Workflow presenting the Data Submission using CSC Submission interface, Entitlements Management System access request and approval, Data access using File System in User Space (FUSE)

Figure 21: Workflow illustrating how data will be submitted and accessed in the Information Commons layer of HEAP

For this demonstration we made use of video demo to illustrate how a researcher can:

- encrypt and submit data to the Information Commons using the Data Submission Engine provided by CSC;
- Another researcher can request data via the REMS tool;
- access the data in a local environment using a FUSE software - with the mention that the FUSE layer is going to be integrated as part of the SD-Desktop service.

2. Presentation of the REMS (Resource Entitlement Management System) software solution for the EMS component of HEAP.

REMS¹ is a software utilised for managing access rights to resources, such as research datasets.

During this part of the demonstration, we have shown how an applicant can log into the software, fill in the data access application and agree to the dataset's terms of use. The application is circulated inside the system to the resource owner or designated representative for follow-up with additional

¹ <https://github.com/CSCfi/remis>

information in case additional information is required and finally approval when such information is provided by the applicant.

We mentioned that the REMS tool also produces the necessary reports on the applications and the granted data access rights.

3. SD Desktop - remote desktop for secure environment - first public iteration of the CSC SD-Desktop service.

During this third part of the demonstration, we have shown how SD-Desktop can run in a web browser (Firefox is utilised) to access a Virtual Machine (VM) in the ePouta² secure cloud environment and make use of a FUSE tool to stream data submitted to Information Commons on demand.

All these demonstrations spark the discussion of the role of metadata and how different metadata standards will be used to identify and use data submitted in the Information Commons.

Results and next steps

- Revise schemas from European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) and other standards:
 - Schemas are derived from the ENA model explained at: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide/metadata.html> and the whole website provides useful info on the ENA submission <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io>
 - JSON schemas done for CSC use cases:
 - [ENA Analysis](#)
 - [ENA Dataset](#)
 - [ENA Experiment](#)
 - [ENA Run](#)
 - [ENA Sample](#)
 - [ENA Study](#)
 - other that might be helpful
 - [ENA DAC](#)
 - [ENA Policy](#)
 - Information on the EGA metadata API is available at: <https://ega-archive.org/metadata/how-to-use-the-api> and <https://ega-archive.org/submission/tools/submitter-portal> which provides the interface for metadata submission
- Investigate more about metadata about analysis of the data for reusability and reproducibility
- Data directly to the Feature Store for the ML

² <https://research.csc.fi/-/epouta>

Stream B

Chair: Anouk Berger

In Stream B, a series of one-to-one structured interviews were held with workshop attendees. The objective of the interviews was to:

- Develop “Personas” to be used to gain a better understanding of the different types of project stakeholders and their training needs. The personas covered the broad HEAP stakeholder categories, such as medical researchers, bioinformatics, IT specialists and public citizens (template included below).
- Conduct a learning needs assessment with HEAP partner representative to understand the learning needs of each persona categories.

Identifying HEAP stakeholders - persona creation

Following the workshop Stream B, the contents of the persona interviews were collated into “Persona” profiles, including information on their background, interests, beliefs and wishes. Personal data was included to make the persona more relatable.

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>What is their research interest in general?</i></p> <p><i>What's in for them in HEAP?</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Do they have specific ethical and legal challenges in the context of HEAP?</i></p>
<p>Stakeholder group:</p> <p>Name:</p> <p>Profession:</p> <p>Age:</p> <p>Personal info:</p> <p><i>country/home town, studies, jobs</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>What resources do they control?</i></p> <p><i>What specific expertise do they have that they can share within HEAP?</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>What do they need - information/guidance/training - so that they can deliver what they are supposed to within HEAP ?</i></p>

Figure 22: Personas template [5]

Additionally, the following Figure shows an example of the persona, an ICT scientist working with data, defining his interests, requirements and needs of and within the project.

	<p>INTERESTS</p> <p><i>Designing and building interoperable IT tools that can be combined with each other.</i></p> <p><i>Designing simple IT tools for data providers (non-IT specialists) to use.</i></p>	<p>ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS</p> <p><i>Needs to understand the legal and ethical implications (e.g. GDPR), and take these considerations into account while developing IT solutions.</i></p> <p><i>Does not handle real data in the course of his job.</i></p>
<p>HEAP stakeholder group:</p> <p><i>ICT scientist</i></p> <p>Name:</p> <p><i>Markus Plass</i></p> <p>Profession:</p> <p><i>Software developer</i></p> <p>Learning Needs Assessment category:</p> <p><i>System designer</i></p> <p>Age range:</p> <p><i>30-40</i></p> <p>Personal info:</p> <p><i>Lives in Graz, Austria. Studied computer sciences</i></p>	<p>POWERS / EXPERTISE</p> <p><i>System analysis and software tools development: gathering requirements from different user groups (both user and application side).</i></p>	<p>NEEDS</p> <p><i>To understand the needs and requirements of the future users of HEAP.</i></p> <p><i>To understand the level of IT knowledge and experience level of the future users of HEAP.</i></p> <p><i>Training on Hopsworks is needed, both for users and for backend technicians.</i></p>

Figure 23: Sample Persona (ICT Scientist)

Learning Needs Assessment

Another activity of Stream B, in parallel with the persona Interviews, was a Learning Needs Assessment Exercise, again using a one-to-one interview format with selected Work Package representatives. The Learning Needs Assessment sought to identify training needs of the target audiences by

listing, per stakeholder group, the prerequisite knowledge and skills needed to be a competent user of the HEAP platform, and any related training requirements.

Members of the “Researcher” target audience (bioinformaticians) also contributed, to highlight their learning needs and expectations from the HEAP platform.

The benefits of the Learning Needs Assessment approach are to:

- Highlight the expertise within the HEAP consortia available to develop learning materials
- Identify the skills and knowledge required to become a competent user of the HEAP platform and predicts the learning needs of the HEAP target audiences
- Provide the information required to structure training materials

The table below shows the HEAP specialists and target audience groups who contributed to the Learning Needs Assessment.

HEAP partner/WP	Key topic specialism
MLC, WP 2 Ethics and Regulations	Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues
MUG, WP7 Data Interoperability and Sharing	Data harmonisation and curation – FAIR data principles
Logical Clocks, WP6 – Informatic platform and Knowledge Engine	HEAP Data Management and analysis services
CSC, WP10 – Secure infrastructure for Big Data	HEAP Data Management and analysis services (HEAP data processor)
University of Innsbruck, WP8, Epigenomics	Bioinformatics (HEAP data processor)
University if Warsaw, WP9, Microbiomics	Bioinformatics (HEAP data processor)

WP6 - Informatics platform and knowledge engine		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
Data Owner/Controller(s)	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of how the data can be used.	Need to learn to how give different types of access (read-only, read-write, etc) to users to data. Learn how to use CSC services(Authorization/REMS).
Data Stewards/Curators	No programming skills reqd. Need domain knowledge of the data that they are curating.	Need to understand how to design metadata templates for artifacts (files, tables, features). Need to undersatnd how to start jobs and analyze (high level) the results. Learn how to use CSC services(SDA uploading/access).
Bioinformaticians	Are able to program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics.	Need to learn to use Jupyter notebooks and the Hopsworks platform to manage data and libraries. May need to learn to write workflows (Airflow). Learn how to use CSC services(SDA uploading/access).
Data Engineering Bioinformaticians	Are able to program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics. Work with large volumes of data, so need to learn data parallel programming (Spark).	Need to learn how to store and process large volumes of data. Learn how to use CSC services(SDA uploading/access)..
Machine Learning Bioinformaticians	Are able to program (Python). Domain knowledge of bioinformatics. Use machine learning to build predictive models.	Need to learn how to train models, evaluate models, and deploy/use models. Learn how to use CSC services(SDA uploading/access)..
System Administrator	Knows Unix/Linux operating system and how to manage servers and software.	Installation and configuration of Hopsworks and CSC resources. Learn how to use CSC services.
WP7 - Data interoperability and data sharing		
Stakeholder/audience group	Prerequisite knowledge/skills	Related training requirements
data providers	FAIR principles	presentation BYOD real training - self assessment service (send the form + Q/A session to get explanations on the questions)
	skills on specific useful tools (to be defined). which tool to provide for the people to do their work better. BUT need to know what people working on data need. For example how to use molgenis (sharable sheets)	training on the tools
		how to use various communication channels for the consortium (incl. social media, tweets/writing stories, etc...) / communication guidelines
		how to use zenodo (to put stuff there - press releases, youtube video... guidance)
	aware of what is in the platform (catalogue) know the governance of the platform to request access to data (through specific proposal) - to be checked (Heimo's view)	

Figure 24: Example of stakeholders, prerequisite knowledge for using HEAP and related training needs

Following these two exercises, the following table was created, showing a list of the personas, and their associated learning needs:

Persona details/HEAP Work Package	Interaction with HEAP (data provider/data processor/system designer) and brief summary of learning needs
Epidemiologist Associated with the data cohorts in WPs 3,4,5,8	Data provider. May need support in using AI.
Biologist/medical researcher Associated with the data cohorts in WPs 3,4,5,8	Data provider. May need support in using AI.
Biobank manager -Associated with the data cohorts in WPs 3,4,5,8	Data provider. May need support in using AI.
Bioinformatician WP 8 and 9 (Epigenomics, Microbiomics).	Data processor. Curates data, upstream processing.

<p>Applied AI users Potentially all platform users. WPs 3,4,5,8,9</p>	<p>Data processor. Refines algorithms/weighting for downstream data processing.</p>
<p>ICT scientist Associated with WPs 6,10,9.</p>	<p>-System designer/data processor. -No learning needs as they will not be an end user of the platform. -Will contribute to the development of technical learning materials and events for data providers and processors.</p>
<p>Ethical expert. Associated with WP2 – Ethics and Regulations.</p>	<p>-System designer. -No learning needs as they will not be an end user of the platform. -Will contribute to the development of Ethical/Legal learning materials and events for data providers and processors.</p>
<p>Public – citizen</p>	<p>-No direct interaction with the HEAP platform -Will benefit from the outcomes of HEAP</p>

Figure 25: Definition of personas and their learning needs

Next steps include:

- Gather more details on knowledge/skills needed, use the platform/tools to structure future training interventions
- Develop training and communication/dissemination plans
- Develop a paper on the use of personas in the medical research context, to be submitted for publication (journal tbc)

Self-Assessment-Service

Another feature of Stream B was an informative session on the FAIR Self-Assessment-Service, a tool for researchers for evaluating and assessing their data and metadata to meet the FAIR standard. The aim of this was to help researchers and the project partners to understand the reason for the establishment of the SAS and the technical and scientific terminology, which is used within the Assessment.

At that time, the SAS state included the establishment of a RedCap file including all the data necessary to be asked in order to improve the status of the data in the respective cohorts.

FAIR Data Self Assessment Tool

Resize font:

[Returning?](#)

The project HEAP provides a research resource for the integrated and efficient analysis of the human exposome. One primary outcome of the project is the complete process for obtaining actionable knowledge from the following sustainable cohorts: 1) a nation-wide maternity cohort 2) a large cervical screening cohort 3) the systematic collection of consumer purchasing receipts linked to health outcomes 4) a HPV vaccination cohort and 5) a wearable data collection study.

The collected data is based on FAIR-Principles, which means the data has to be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable [[FAIR Data Maturity Model](#), [Specification and Guidelines 2020](#)].

In order to assess the quality of the used data, we established a self-assessment guide for every operating partner in the HEAP project. This guide provides fundamental questions/principles for the assessment of the deployed data in the cohorts. The following self-assessment questionnaire is divided into the four aforementioned relevant FAIR-Principles:

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable
- Re-usable

Please answer the following questions to assess your standards. By sending us the answers we can evaluate the quality of your data. Should you have any question, please don't hesitate to contact us [[mail-address](#)].

Information about data provider

Name of contact person * must provide value	<input type="text"/>
Name and type of cohort * must provide value	<input type="text"/>
Institution details (name, address) * must provide value	<input type="text"/> Expand
Email * must provide value	<input type="text"/>
Phone * must provide value	<input type="text"/>

Figure 26: First draft of the SAS integrated in RedCap

Fotos

4.2 BYOD-Workshop #2

The second BYOD-workshop took place between October 18th and October 20th, 2021. Initially planned as a face-to-face meeting, the workshop was another victim of the pandemic and had to take place online once again. Similar to the first BYOD-workshop, the second virtual get-to-together was set to be training sessions among the HEAP partners in order to define the HEAP cohorts metadata and thus intensify the establishment of the HEAP master catalogue/metadata catalogue, as well as exchange insights about the progress of HEAP informatics platform.

See below the agenda for the 2nd Bring-Your-Own-Data workshop. It is derived in plenary sessions for all participants, and parallel streams (Streams A, B and C) which focus on a specific topic, see Stream A and following.

18.10.2021	Plenary
13:00-13:30	Hello and welcome
13:30-17:00	Training session
	“Story telling” stream - introduction and goals Presentation from NRG, ways of working and video development Story telling session demonstration
19.10.2021	Plenary
9:00 - 9:30 (CEST)	Introduction (JD), goals of the meeting, Zoom housekeeping, Introduction round (HM)
9:30-10:00 (CEST)	DMP update (revise, new cohort)
10:00-10:30	Metadata Catalogue
10:30-11:00	Coffee break
11:00-11:30	HW update
11:30-12:00	CSC update
12:00-13:00	Lunch

Jamboree Streams			
	Stream A (AB)	Stream B (PN)	Stream C (RM)
13:00 – 17:00 (CEST)	Data story telling One-on-One Sessions https://iarc.zoom.us/j/8637989367	BYO-Metadata established cohorts (HPV, Maternity, Cervical Screening) Zoom link: https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/91757957885 Template: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1mmCak1iXnlTFGLtZ2cX_o0Y1hiwZFYvKsgPHWLO1jCY/edit?usp=sharing	BYO-Metadata experimental cohorts (LifeStyle, Consumer, Wearable) Zoom link: https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/94221674572 Template: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1mmCak1iXnlTFGLtZ2cX_o0Y1hiwZFYvKsgPHWLO1jCY/edit?usp=sharing
20.10.2020	Plenary		
9:00 - 09:30 (CEST)	Report on day 2 (3 streams) and conclusion from the stream chairs (each 10 mins) Stream A: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1gNnacG6nA15OXrnZKhk7mwP5PdmTul0Z Stream B: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1kTZP6eF_GhA8q7S85Tmu9aQHVFRQ3LAPPDM0mvTZuig/edit#slide=id.p3 Stream C: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jT1hJ0M2MYkxqnR9jHwJLabnJdXNDLWBsPzDKwPn5O0/edit?usp=sharing		
09:30 - 10:30 (CEST)	HopsWorks demonstration - data ingest and feature extraction (Hive); registration to further workshops		
10:30-11:00 (CEST)	Coffee break		
11:00-12:00	CSC SD Desktop demonstration; registration to further workshops		
12:00-13:00	Lunch		

13:00-13:30	SAS training https://heap.bibbox.org/surveys/?s=XC8YLX8W8R		
13:30-15:00	Stream A (AB)	Stream B (PN)	Stream C (RM)
general: wishlist for F2F meetings	Data storytelling Conclusion https://iarc.zoom.us/j/8637989367	Established Cohort Conclusion https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/91757957885	Experimental Cohort Conclusion https://cesnet.zoom.us/j/94221674572
15:00-15:30	Coffee break		
15:30-open end	Wrap up and presentation of stream results		

Attendees list of all participants of the 2nd BYOD-workshop and which of the three parallel streams they attended:

Institution	Name	Attendance
KI	Joakim Dillner	Stream A
KI	Helena Andersson	Stream A
KI	Roxana Merino Martinez	Stream C
KI	Suyesh Amatya	Stream C
KI	Augustin Ure	Stream B
KI	Sara Arroyo Muhr	Stream B
KI	Allison Zhang	Stream C
SSI	Frederik Trier Möller	Stream A, Stream C
MLC	Martin Boeckhout	Stream A
MUG	Heimo Müller	Stream A
MUG	Andreas Holzinger	Stream B
MUG	Bettina Kipperer	Stream A
MUG	Markus Plass	Stream B
MUG	Robert Reihs	Stream C

Institution	Name	Attendance
MUG	Patrick Nitsche	Stream B
ICM	Piotr Bala	Stream C
LC	Jim Dowling	Stream C
LC	Alex Ormenisan	Stream B
IARC	Anouk Berger	Stream A
IARC	Zisis Kozlakidis	Stream A
IARC	Heather Coombs	Stream A
INSB	Chiara Maria Stella Herzog	Stream A, Stream C
INSB	Charlotte Vavourakis	Stream A, Stream C
CSC	Stefan Negru	Stream C
Tampere	Matti Lehtinen	Stream B
Tampere	Ville Pimenoff	Stream B, Stream C

Plenary Stream

This section summarizes the discussions and workshops during the plenary stream as well as the agreed upon key messages.

18th of October, 2021

After an address of welcome by Roxana Merino Martinez and Heimo Müller, the training session started with Annouk Berger and Heather Coombs explaining the goals of Stream A to the participants (see Stream A). In order to help with the development of scripts for the FAIR videos, WP11 hired NRG (<https://nrg-digital.co.uk/>), a visual communications agency. In the plenary stream, Robert Edmonds from NRG explained the process of how an animated video is created. The process is as follows:

1. Information, ideation and scripting

The first stage is to understand the client's business and the key message they want to be delivered as well as the target audience for the animation videos. With this information, a first script can be drafted.

2. Storyboarding

With the script approved, NRG starts developing a storyboard, either illustrating each frame or sketching out the action using a line drawn style.

3. Animation, voiceover and music

The storyboard is transformed from stills to moving images, bringing characters to life, giving the icons energy and creating motion in the key graphics.

4. Mastering

Once the animation stage has been signed off, the film goes into mastering and sound mixing where audio effects are added, and the master voiceover is recorded.

To give the interviewees of Stream A an example of what type of stories could be of interest for the FAIR video scripts, Zisis Kozlakidis introduced his experience with FAIR data management and his experience with the lack thereof.

After this, the topic shifted to a more general debate with Andreas Holzinger sparking a lively discussion about the future of the HEAP data regarding its potential for Artificial Intelligence and feature extraction. This in turn leads to the topic of data longevity and sustainability: the question of what would happen to the HEAP data once the project will end.

The plenary stream was closed by Heimo Müller announcing the HEAP annual meeting in Graz, Austria in February (note: since then, the date has been postponed due to COVID-19). The stream discussed key points like:

- participants
- public talks (possible speakers and topics)
- combining the annual meeting with the next BYOD workshop
- HEAP internal presentation about the opportunities when combining data from the new and experimental cohorts with the one from a biobank related cohort

19th of October, 2021

The 2nd day of the workshop was started off by the HEAP project lead, Joakim Dillner who officially welcomed everybody to the workshop and explained the goals of the meeting. Heimo Müller continued, reminding the plenary of what BYOD is about (see Figure 27) and started an introduction of participants where everybody consecutively stated their name and affiliation as well as their role within HEAP and professional and personal background.

BYOD

BRING YOUR OWN DATA

inspired from the **Bring Your Own Device** movements

- **Real Data**
Attendees bring their “real data” with real problems
- **Hackathon Style**
hands-on, coding, no presentations, mockups, API tests
- **Connectathon Style**
Check the interoperability of data and interfaces
- **Jamboree Style**
no fixed agenda, work in a camp, evening sessions

Figure 27: Definition 'BYOD'

Heimo Müller went on with a booster talk of the Data Management Plan, focusing on the distinction between data and metadata. Giving a short summary about all cohorts should help the participants understand what the other cohorts are working on. This also officially introduced the LifeStyle cohort to the whole HEAP team as this cohort joined the project in 2020.

Data Management Plan

A data object is like an onion

Figure 28: Data object

Patrick Nitsche gave an introduction about the HEAP metadata catalogue. The catalogue will make metadata about the HEAP Information Commons and the Data & Feature warehouse available to stakeholders and the general public. This will also improve data longevity as well as facilitate new research and new discoveries. Since there was some confusion prior to the workshop, it was specifically stated that the metadata catalogue will only contain the metadata fields of the HEAP cohorts, but no actual data, work package 7 decided on the tool Molgenis [6] [7]. Molgenis was developed to help researchers find, capture, exchange, manage and analyse scientific data. It is highly customizable which allows it to be tailored to the specific needs of exposome related research metadata. The included catalogue app allows for easy discovery of the HEAP project as well as its cohorts and their metadata fields. A short presentation of a reference project should give everybody a first impression of what the HEAP metadata catalogue could look like and what information needs to be gathered in the Streams B and C in order to get there.

Heimo Müller gave an overview of the current state of the FAIR Self-Assessment-Service (SAS). This service is aimed at HEAP data owners to evaluate their “FAIRness level”, showing how well data and data management practises perform under each of the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable).

To evaluate the FAIRness level, work package 7 developed an online survey where one has to answer questions and statements regarding the FAIR principles. The possible answers range from “0-not applicable” to “4-fully implemented”. The survey results are then sent by mail to the participant as a pdf report. The report descriptively displays the results as spidergraphs, one graph per FAIR concept, showing areas which need further work.

20th of October, 2021

The third day of the workshop started with a presentation of the platform Hopsworks, which was already introduced in the first BYOD workshop by WP6 colleagues. The talk began with the current state of Hopsworks (HW) and afterwards a detailed demonstration about the Informatics Platform was provided.

Hopsworks Updates

The HEAP testbed has been upgraded from Hopsworks version 1.4 to version 2.4. This upgrade includes several new features and improvements. The upgrade also includes specific customization for the HEAP testbed, including support for CSC Fuse Client as well as customization to allow running jobs relying on PCJ and Diamond libraries.

Hopsworks provides several updated services and new services. Among the existing services, the most notable one is a brand-new UI providing a more user-friendly interface.

Figure 29: Hopsworks Architecture

The most important updates are towards the feature store and the models registry. The feature store updates include expectations, alerts, statistics, activity log and new storage connectors. A new mechanism allows for custom user creation of Elasticsearch indices, visualisation, and analysis of the data of these indices within Kibana or Spark.

The new UI provides a new, more capable user interface for the feature store, storage connectors, jobs, Jupyter notebooks, schematized tags, and provenance.

The new features include a prototype for RStudio support as well as customizable docker image for jobs.

The documentation support has also been improved in the new version and now also includes documentation, examples and a community forum:

- <https://docs.hopsworks.ai>
- <https://examples.hopsworks.ai>
- <https://community.hopsworks.ai>

Hopsworks Demonstration

1. Access to Project's custom Elasticsearch indices

In this part of the demonstration, we show the possibility of creating custom indices and writing/reading data from it using the JSON Web

Tokens(JWT) provided by the platform. These tokens are tied to the <project, user> combination. The same token cannot be used by a different user, member of the same project or by the same user with a different project that they are part of. The contents of these indices can later be explored with Kibana visualisations.

```
elastic_access.ipynb
[1]: from hops import elasticsearch, hdfs
Starting Spark application
ID          YARN Application ID  Kind  State  Spark UI  Driver log
11 application_1634545581415_0023  pyspark  idle  Link      Link
SparkSession available as 'spark'.

[2]: path = "hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1"
df = spark.read.option("header", "true").csv(path)
df.write.format('org.elasticsearch.spark.sql').options(**elasticsearch.get_elasticsearch_config("logs-heap")).mode("overwrite").save()

[3]: reader = spark.read.format("org.elasticsearch.spark.sql").options(**elasticsearch.get_elasticsearch_config("newindex"))
df = reader.load()
df.show()

+----+-----+-----+-----+
|_c0|age|first_name|last_name|      path|
+----+-----+-----+-----+
| 0| 1|    Alex|Ormenisan|hdfs:///Projects/...|
| 1| 2|    Jim|Dowling|hdfs:///Projects/...|
| 2| 3|  Roxana|Martinez|hdfs:///Projects/...|
+----+-----+-----+-----+

[10]: reader = spark.read.format("org.elasticsearch.spark.sql").options(**elasticsearch.get_elasticsearch_config("newindex"))
df = reader.load()
df.show()

+----+-----+-----+-----+
|_c0|age|first_name|last_name|      path|
+----+-----+-----+-----+
| 0| 1|    Alex|Ormenisan|hdfs:///Projects/...|
| 1| 2|    Jim|Dowling|hdfs:///Projects/...|
| 2| 3|  Roxana|Martinez|hdfs:///Projects/...|
+----+-----+-----+-----+
```

2. Access to Project's custom relation tables with Hive

In this part of the demonstration, we show the possibility of creating and accessing custom relational tables within Hive. Hive enables data summarization, querying and analysis of data in a language similar to SQL. Hive stores its tables within the HopsFS distributed file system of Hopsworks so it is highly scalable. The demonstration includes creating/deleting tables as well as inserting/updating and performing a variety of typical sql queries on the inserted data.

Select Hive Database

Using the spark session you can interact with Hive through the `sql` method on the `sparkSession`, or through auxiliary methods like `.select()` and `.where()`.

Each project that have enabled Hive will automatically have a Hive database created for them, this is the only Hive database that you can access unless someone have shared their database with you.

```
[2]: from hops import hdfs as hopsfs
PROJECT_NAME = hopsfs.project_name()
```

```
[3]: PROJECT_NAME
'test'
```

```
[4]: spark.sql("use " + PROJECT_NAME)
DataFrame[]
```

Create Tables

Tables can be created either by issuing a `CREATE TABLE` statement or by using the `saveAsTable()` method on an existing dataframe. When using `saveAsTable` spark will infer the schema from the dataframe and do the `CREATE TABLE` for you.

```
[5]: spark.sql("show tables").show()
+-----+-----+-----+
|database|tableName|isTemporary|
+-----+-----+-----+
+-----+-----+-----+
```

3. Schematized tags usage

In this part of the demonstration, we showed how to use schematized tags within the Hopsworks platforms. We showed how to create the schemas and describe the capabilities of JSON schemas implementing <https://json-schema.org/> as reference. We showed how to attach, update, remove tags as well how to search for files based on the attached tags.

```
[7]: from hops import dataset, hdfs

[ ]: path = hdfs.project_path() + "Alex/patient1"
     path

[ ]: dataset.get_tags(path)

[12]: tag_value = {"first_name": "Heap", "last_name": "Ormenisan", "age": 40}
      dataset.add_tag(path, "person", tag_value)

[14]: dataset.get_tags(path)
      {'person': '{"first_name": "Heap", "last_name": "Ormenisan", "age": 40}' }

[8]: dataset.get_tag(path, "person")

[8]: {'person': '{"first_name": "Jim", "last_name": "Ormenisan", "age": 40}' }

[14]: dataset.remove_tag(path, "person")
```

We manually create the csv file and write it to Hopsworks

```
[16]: import pandas as pd

[17]: data = { "path": [path + "/alex", path + "/jim", path + "/roxana"],
              "first_name" : ["Alex", "Jim", "Roxana"],
              "last_name" : ["Ormenisan", "Dowling", "Martinez"],
              "age" : [1,2,3]
            }
      df = pd.DataFrame(data)
      df
```

```
[17]:
```

	path	first_name	last_name	age
0	hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/alex	Alex	Ormenisan	1
1	hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/jim	Jim	Dowling	2
2	hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/roxana	Roxana	Martinez	3

During the demonstration, we also showed how to easily import large amounts of metadata and attach it as tags to existing files.

We read the csv file and use the columns to build as a tag which we then attach to directories/files

```
[20]: df.to_csv(path + '/persons1.csv')
```

```
[21]: read_data = pd.read_csv(path + '/persons.csv')
read_data.head()
```

Unnamed: 0		path	first_name	last_name	age
0	0	hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/alex	Alex	Ormenisan	1
1	1	hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/jim	Jim	Dowling	2
2	2	hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/roxana	Roxana	Martinez	3

```
[23]: for index, row in df.iterrows():
tag_value = {"first_name": row["first_name"], "last_name": row["last_name"], "age": row["age"]}
dataset.add_tag(row["path"], "person", tag_value)
print(row["path"])

hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/alex
hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/jim
hdfs:///Projects/test/Alex/patient1/roxana
```

```
[24]: for index, row in df.iterrows():
print(dataset.get_tag(row["path"], "person"))

{'person': '{"first_name": "Alex", "last_name": "Ormenisan", "age": 1}'}
{'person': '{"first_name": "Jim", "last_name": "Dowling", "age": 2}'}
{'person': '{"first_name": "Roxana", "last_name": "Martinez", "age": 3}'}
```

4. Provenance

During this part of the demonstration, we showed how the creation and usage of feature groups and training datasets can be visualised within the Hopsworks platform in order to better understand the usage patterns of data.

SD-Desktop Demonstration

The demonstration started with a brief recap of the HEAP Reference Architecture, as a way to set the stage for the services that will be introduced and how they will be integrated in the HEAP platform.

This was followed by introducing the recently launched CSC Sensitive Data (SD) Services in Open Beta and their use case.

An overview of the services is given: "CSC Sensitive Data Services for Research are designed to support secure sensitive data management

through web-user interfaces accessible from the user's own computer." The services demonstrated will be:

- SD Connect - Used for data upload (and sharing with other researchers);
- SD Desktop - Remote desktop environment for accessing and working with uploaded files in Hopsworks software.

Launching the services represents a concrete step towards implementation of the HEAP "platform", as part of the Information Commons layer, mentioned in the Reference Architecture.

The scenario presented was aimed towards promoting collaboration across research organisations, a scenario relevant to HEAP project as many researchers are part of different organizations. CSC illustrated how each individual service can be accessed and used at the end highlighting the connection between the SD-Connect and SD-Desktop, how data uploaded through SD-Connect can be accessed securely in a SD-Desktop VM which runs on the ePouta secure cloud infrastructure.

Figure 30: CSC Sensitive Data Services for Research³

The concluding part of the demonstration was aimed towards discussing concrete steps towards integration between CSC SD services and Hopsworks.

At the end of the demonstration a survey was conducted on interest for organizing a hands-on workshop on CSC services for HEAP. The result of the survey was an overwhelming interest in organizing such a workshop in 2022.

Stream A

Chair: Anouk Berger

The idea of FAIR data videos (further explained under 3.1) was further developed, producing short clips in which the FAIR principles are explained in an engaging way to researchers within the HEAP project, as well as for the external medical audience. To make the scripts for the FAIR videos more diverse and to link back to HEAP and its cohorts, researchers from all (in the meanwhile) 6 (further details under Stream C) cohorts were interviewed. In these 20–30-minute talks, the researchers were asked about their experience with making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable - be it positive or negative. The input gathered in Stream A will later be used in the development of the FAIR video scripts.

Stream A prepared questions to ensure that the presented stories would match the FAIR principles:

Findable

- Can you share an example of when you've found it difficult to find the data you needed?
- Why was it so difficult to find what you needed?
- How did you overcome the issue?
- Are there steps you take now to avoid experiencing the same difficulty?
- Conversely, do you have an example of when it has been easy to find data?
- How was that scenario different from the first example?
- What has it taught you about ensuring findability of data?

Accessible

- Can you share an example of when you've found it difficult to access the data you needed?
- Why was it so difficult to gain access to what you needed?
- How did you overcome the issue?
- Are there steps you take now to avoid experiencing the same difficulty?
- Conversely, do you have an example of when it has been easy to access data?
- How was that scenario different from the first example?
- What has it taught you about ensuring accessibility of data for everyone who needs it?

Interoperable

- Can you share an example of when you've found it difficult to combine data from different data streams – or when you've struggled to extract the specific data you needed from a 'data lake'?
- Why was it so difficult to combine or extract what you needed?
- How did you overcome the issue?

- Are there steps you take now to avoid experiencing the same difficulty?
- Conversely, do you have an example of when it has been easy to combine data from different data streams – or when it's been particularly easy to extract the specific data you needed from a 'data lake'?
- How was that scenario different from the first example?
- What has it taught you about ensuring interoperability of data?

Reusable

- Can you share an example of when you've found it difficult to reuse data for different purposes?
- Why was it so difficult?
- How did you overcome the issue?
- Are there steps you take now to avoid experiencing the same difficulty?
- Conversely, do you have an example of when it has been easy to reuse diverse data for multiple purposes?
- How was that scenario different from the first example?
- What has it taught you about ensuring reusability of data?

Stream B

Chair: Patrick Nitsche

Targeted Cohorts and representatives:

- Cervical screening cohort; Sara Arroyo Muhr
- Maternity cohort; Ville Pimenoff
- HPV vaccination cohort; Ville Pimenoff

Stream B focused on the already established, biobank linked cohorts. The stream started off by a definition of the status quo for each cohort, describing the current workflow from taking samples from patients or study participants, to be analysed. This already sparked a lively discussion between participants regarding the similarities between the cohorts.

Before talking about the current metadata model, it was specifically emphasised that it was not the goal of the workshop to design or improve the cohort's metadata model. The metadata catalogue, and therefore the discussion in this stream, should reflect the metadata fields "as-is".

To facilitate the discussion regarding metadata fields, a template was provided prior to the workshop which should help collect information about a cohort's metadata fields in a standardised and structured way.

In addition to the metadata fields, Stream B also discussed possible aggregated values that could be used in the catalogue on a cohort level to further advertise its data. An example for such an aggregated value could be the number of participants or samples in the cohort. Attendees of Stream B discussed what values would be best suited for each cohort and possible mechanisms to keep the aggregated values up to date over the lifetime of a cohort.

Stream C

Chair: Roxana Merino Martinez

Targeted Cohorts and representatives:

- LifeStyle cohort; Chiara Maria Stella Herzog, Charlotte Vavourakis
- Wearable Data collection study; Ville Pimenoff
- Consumer cohort; Frederik Trier Möller

Stream C focused on the new and experimental HEAP cohorts.

First, we have to introduce another cohort to the already existing 5 cohorts: the lifestyle cohort, which gathers data from up to 200 women. The study investigates the effect of lifestyle changes (smoking cessation and/or interval fasting with or without ketogenic food supplements with guided, targeted exercises) over a period of 6 months (optionally 12 and 18 months) on disease- and age-associated biological signatures and body functions. In addition to regular health checkups, participants are provided a smart watch, which will record bio-parameters such as heart rate or stress level.

Stream C was mainly concerned with working on the Metadata templates provided by the consortium to collect the data fields and attributes for the different experimental cohorts. This is the basis for the external catalogue of metadata provided by HEAP. This opened the floor to a discussion and analysis of fields for harmonization of the metadata and standardisation of metadata.

The following example represents the HEAP Metadata Template provided with information from the Consumer cohort:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Entity	Attribute	Description	Type	Example	Note				
2		participant	anonymized ID	integer	123					
3		receipt	receipt ID	char	Receipt_3773					
4		itemname	description of product from receipt	char	banana					
5		itemnumber	itemnumber or GTIN13/EAN/UPC	integer	5710815000014					
6		category	merchants category	integer	882					
7		amount	number of items bought	integer	1					
8		itemPrice	price in dkk	numeric	12.95	Standardized for full 13 digit GTINs shorter integers often local and merchant specific				
9		rabat	discount	numeric	-1.00	Incomplete, and often different from merchant to merchant, missing data				
10		purchase date	date of purchase	date	2021-02-01					
11		weekno		integer	5					
12		monthno		integer	2					
13		yearno		integer	2021					
14		MerchantName	name of merchant	char	supermarket name					

Figure 31: Example participant consumer data

Stream B & C - Outlook

All cohort data-owners provided insight in their metadata fields using the provided templates. Starting with this overview of available metadata, work package 7 will develop an exhaustive, internal catalogue using the Molgenis tool. The public metadata catalogue will be derived from it with its

granularity defined later on as some concerns arose whether to share all metadata fields or not. If it is defined that all metadata can be made public, the internal catalogue will be, at the same time, the public one.

The work for the exhaustive, internal catalogue will start with the Cervical Screening cohort and the LifeStyle cohort in a proof-of-concept phase before the other cohorts are being involved. To facilitate ease of communication, the attendees agreed on a slack channel.

Wishlist for the 3rd BYOD workshop

At the end of the 2nd Bring-Your-Own-Data workshop, participants were asked what they would wish for in the next workshop. The collected and harmonized answers were as follows:

- Representing the data using the HEAP standardised format from this BOYD
- Import data into Hopsworks for query
- Good definition of features for Machine Learning
- Design and implement some models and get prediction
- How to represent consumer data
- How to analyse the consumer data using Machine Learning
- Hackathon type BYOD; go through the workflow from data input, search, analysing
- Make the 3rd BYOD in person, maybe in February or March 2022
- Bring real data and do science together - researchers from different domains offer a new point of view, collaboratively develop new ideas

Fotos

5 Outlook

During the first 24-months of the HEAP project, WP7 worked on establishing the main objectives from the Data Management Plan (DMP) including Standards, Recommendations, Interoperability Training, the development of a FAIR toolbox, the organization of Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops and the coordination of the liaisons to ESFRI research infrastructures (e.g. ELIXIR, BMRI), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and large-scale coordination projects as EOSC-Life, EJP-RD, GA4GH, GO FAIR, Global BioImaging, Galaxy, Bioconda and RDA, knowledge exchange with all other projects in the Human Exposome cluster.

All deliverables have been submitted according to the time plan, and the progress of WP7 is in line with that set out in the HEAP proposal. In month 5, D7.1 Data Management Plan was created. This month (M25), D7.2 FAIR Toolbox and BYOD workshops will be submitted. Especially the BYOD workshops have been established in great synergy with WP11 (work package on Education and Dissemination), which has been of great support in the creation and performance of the trainings within HEAP.

Next, the main focus is on the establishment of D7.3 Metadata Catalogue and Access Procedures. The web service will include explicit information regarding metadata availability and the possibility of free use of all this data for the purposes of the project. At the end of the project, D7.4 Assessment of Interoperability and Data Quality will describe and further explain how interoperability of the project was successfully achieved by continuing data quality and complying the FAIR principles as well as GDPR-standards. Further BYOD workshops will be held as well for the better implementation and cooperation among all the HEAP project partners.

In this deliverable, we propose using the BIBBOX framework as an external tool that supports several functionalities for data FAIRness, standardisation and management. Reusing the BIBBOX framework, which was extensively developed during the EU project B3Afria (<http://www.b3africa.org/>), not only supports the FAIRification of data before integrating it into the HEAP platform, but also provides researchers with useful open-source tools that are not part of the HEAP and are of great help in the research data management process.

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